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EFFECT OF ANTI-STRESS PREPARATIONS ON THE ROOT MASS OF CHICKPEA (CICER ARIETINUM)

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Аннотация. Сорные растения снижают урожайность сельскохозяйственных культур, ухудшают качество продукции. При средней засоренности посевов урожайность снижается на 20-25%, а при сильной засоренности вообще можно не получит урожая.

Ключвые слова: гербицид, препарат, двудольные растения, сорные растение, нут, биологическая эффективность.

Abstract. Types and quantities of weeds in mosh fields, rate of occurrence. The Weeds reduce the productivity of the agricultural cultures, worsen the quality to product. Under average sowing productivity falls on 20-25%, but under strong in general possible not to get the harvests.

Key words: herbicide, preparation, dicotyledonous plants, weed plant, corn, and biological effectiveness.

The chickpea root system consists of a taproot and lateral roots. The taproot penetrates the soil to a depth of 1-1.5 m, while the majority of the root mass is located primarily in the arable soil layer. A soil density of 1.1-1.3 g/cm³ is considered favorable for the normal development of nodule bacteria in the root system. Bacterial nodules begin to form on the roots 7-10 days after germination.

The chickpea plant, through symbiosis with bacteria such as *Mesorhizobium ciceri* and *Mesorhizobium mediterraneum*, accumulates nitrogen from the atmosphere during the growth period through biological nitrogen fixation via root nodules, providing 8-10 tons of local fertilizer. Most of the accumulated nitrogen is lost with the crop, 25-40% remains in the soil with plant residues, without organic matter, and some is lost in the process of denitrification.

Under unfavorable conditions, legumes meet their nitrogen needs from soil reserves. Under such conditions, nodule bacteria function poorly, and the accumulated nitrogen cannot meet the plant's needs. Highly active nodule bacteria are pink or red, while weakly active ones are white or light green. Nitragin and rizotorfin are used to increase nodule bacteria activity.

Experiments show that differences in the cross-sectional area of the varieties were also significant. The relatively high values observed in 2022 indicate that climatic conditions (precipitation, humidity) that year allowed for active root development. The Polvon variety had higher root weight than the Zumrad variety in all years, demonstrating its high genetic potential and stress tolerance. Furthermore, a root weight of 2,0–4,5 g is considered the optimal physiological indicator for

chickpeas. Large root mass ensures stable plant growth throughout the growing season, produces more tubers and increases yield.

The results of field experiments conducted in 2022–2024 on irrigated lightgray soils in the Kibray district of the Tashkent region showed that various combinations of herbicides and biostimulants had a significant impact on the root mass of the chickpea varieties 'Zumrad' and 'Polvon'. For both varieties, the preparations played an important role in the development of the plant root system, especially the results obtained with the use of biostimulants were higher than in the control variants (Table 1).

In the variants treated with preparations containing the active substance pendamethalin + biostimulant, the root mass of the 'Zumrad' variety was 2,5 g in 2022, 2,6 g in 2023, and 2,7 g in 2024, with a three-year average of 2,6 g. For the 'Polvon' variety, these figures were 2,6 g, 2,7 g, and 2,8 g. an average of 2,7 g. These data indicate that the Polvon variety has a more stable root system in relation to stressful conditions. In the variants of the same group, where the preparation Stomp (2,0 l/ha) was applied, the root weight reached 3,0 g for the Zumrad variety and 3,1 g for the Polvon variety. The Yastar variant with a dose of 3,0 l/ha showed the highest values: 3,5 g for the Zumrad variety and 3,7 g for the Polvon variety. A similar decrease in root weight (3,9–4,1 g) was observed for the Yastar variant with a dose of 6.0 l/ha, which indicates that this high dose had an insignificant inhibitory effect on root growth.

A similar trend was observed when using products that combined the active ingredient Prometrin with a biostimulant. In the control variants, the root weight was 2,6 g for the Zumrad variety and 2,7 g for the Polvon variety. For the Polvon variety treated with Gezagard (2,5 l/ha), the figure was 3,1 g, which is 0,5 g higher than in the control. The most effective result was recorded for the Gambit variant (1,5 l/ha), where the root weight was 4,1 g for the Zumrad variety and 4,3 g for the Polvon variety. Also, for the Gambit variant (3,0 l/ha), the root weight was 3,6 g for the Polvon variety and 3,8 g for the Zumrad variety, with a slight tendency to decrease at higher doses. This means that the optimal dose of herbicides used in combination with biostimulants stimulates active root growth, but excess can have the opposite effect.

Similar patterns were observed in studies with products containing the active ingredient Imazapyr and a biostimulant. In the control treatment, the root mass of Zumrad was 2,6 g, while that of Polvon was 2,7 g. In treatments treated with Zeta 10% susc.c. (0,5 l/ha), the root mass of Zumrad was 3,2 g, while that of Polvon was 3,3 g. The Pilot gold 10% susc.c. (0,5 l/ha) treatment showed the highest results: 4,2 g for Zumrad and 4,4 g for Polvon. Similar results were observed with the Pilot gold variant at a rate of 0,6 l/ha: 3,8 g of root mass for the Polvon variety and 4,0 g for the Zumrad variety. These data confirm that biostimulants activate stress defense mechanisms and contribute to an increase in root biomass.

Table 1

Effect of herbicide and biostimulant application on chickpea root weight, in grams.

Option	Names of chickpea varieties	Years, (weight of chickpea root), gramms			On average, grams
		2022	2023	2024	
Pendamentalin + Ekobiosfera Organik plyus					
Herbicide-free control	Zumrad	2,5	2,6	2,7	2,6
	Polvon	2,6	2,7	2,8	2,7
Stomp 2,0 l/ha (control)	Zumrad	2,9	3,0	3,1	3,0
	Polvon	3,0	3,1	3,2	3,1
Yastar 3,0 l/ha	Zumrad	3,4	3,5	3,6	3,5
	Polvon	3,6	3,7	3,8	3,7
Yastar 6,0 l/ha	Zumrad	3,8	3,9	4,0	3,9
	Polvon	4,0	4,1	4,2	4,1
Prometrin + Ekobiosfera Organik plyus					
Herbicide-free control	Zumrad	2,5	2,6	2,7	2,6
	Polvon	2,6	2,7	2,8	2,7
Gezagard 2,5 l/ha (control)	Zumrad	3,0	3,1	3,2	3,1
	Polvon	3,1	3,2	3,3	3,2
Gambit 1,5 l/ha	Zumrad	4,0	4,1	4,2	4,1
	Polvon	4,2	4,3	4,4	4,3
Gambit 3,0 l/ha	Zumrad	3,5	3,6	3,7	3,6
	Polvon	3,7	3,8	3,9	3,8
Imazapyr + Ekobiosfera Organik plyus					
Herbicide-free control	Zumrad	2,5	2,6	2,7	2,6
	Polvon	2,6	2,7	2,8	2,7
Zeta 10% sus.k. 0,5 l/ha (control)	Zumrad	3,1	3,2	3,3	3,2
	Polvon	3,2	3,3	3,4	3,3
Pilot gold 0,5 l/ ha	Zumrad	4,1	4,2	4,3	4,2
	Polvon	4,3	4,4	4,5	4,4
Pilot gold 0,6 l/ha	Zumrad	3,7	3,8	3,9	3,8
	Polvon	3,9	4,0	4,1	4,0

When summarizing the experimental results, it was found that the Polvon variety demonstrated higher root mass in almost all treatments than the Zumrad variety. This indicates that this variety possesses a genetically stronger root system and is more resilient to environmental stress. Specifically, treatments with Gambit (1,5–3,0 l/ha) and Pilot Gold 10% 0,5 l/ha demonstrated the highest root mass (4,4 g) for the Polvon variety. This demonstrates the effectiveness of these treatments in

strengthening the root system, accelerating nutrient absorption, and increasing total biomass during the initial stage of chickpea growth.

Also, the high root mass in treatments with Yastar 3,0 l/ha and Pilot Gold 0,5 l/ha indicates that these treatments activate antioxidant systems in plant physiology and maintain osmotic balance in cells. This increases plant resistance to drought, high temperatures, and chemical stress. However, the fact that excessively high doses (for example, Yastar 6.0 l/ha) resulted in a reduction in root mass indicates the need to clearly define the optimal herbicide dosage range.

In conclusion, the conducted research shows that, based on the results of field experiments conducted in 2022–2024 on irrigated gray soils in the Tashkent region, the combined use of herbicides and biostimulants on the chickpea varieties "Zumrad" and "Polvon" significantly enhanced root system development. The experimental results indicate that the effect of the treatments directly depends on the year's conditions: in 2023, due to unfavorable climate conditions (low temperatures and excess moisture), root mass decreased, whereas in 2024, under optimal temperature and humidity conditions, root biomass reached its maximum values.

Herbicides based on pendamethalin, prometryn, and imazapyr, when used in combination with biostimulants, resulted in an average increase in root mass of 0,4–2,1 g. In particular, the best results were demonstrated by Pilot gold (0.5–0.6 l/ha), Gambit (1,5 l/ha), and Yastar (3,0 l/ha). With these treatments, the root mass of the Polvon variety reached approximately 3,9–4,1 g, while that of the Zumrad variety reached approximately 3,7–3,9 g. The Polvon variety demonstrated high resistance even under stressful conditions and gained a biological advantage due to the formation of a deeper root system.

Overall, the correct combination of herbicides and biostimulants stimulated root development, creating a favorable physiological basis for nutrient uptake by the chickpea plant, nitrogen fixation, and increased overall productivity. Thus, the results from 2022–2024 provide a reliable scientific basis for identifying stress-resistant variants with high biological activity.

References

1. Turdieva N., Sayfullaeva N and others. Influence of herbicidal norms on cereal yield while sowing on corn fields. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. ISSN 1475-7192. IJPR 10404 May 2020. 4249-4253 p.

2. Turdieva N, Tursunov S, Sayfullaeva N Материалы международной научно практической конференции, посвященной 65-летию работы кафедры растениеводства ФГБОУВО Ижевская ГСХА Удмуртии. 19-22 ноября 2019. Город Ижевск. – С.292- 298.

3. Turdieva N., Togaeva D., Bahodirovna Sh. Biological Efficiency Herbicides Against One-Year Perennial Dicotyledonous Weed On Sowing Maize Fields. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643- 9670 Vol. 5 Issue 2, February - 2021, - P.204-206.

4. Turdieva N. Sayfullaeva N and others Biological Efficiency Of Herbicide (Elymis) Against Weeds In Crops Corn. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 3, March - 2021, - P. 179-182.

5. Turdieva N. and others Type, Ratio, Damaging Degrees Of Weeds And Effectiveness Of Herbicides Against To The Weeds, Which Meet Among Legume Crops. International Journal of Academic Management Science Research (IJAMSR) ISSN: 2643-900X Vol. 5 Issue 3, March - 2021, - P. 66-69.

6. Muminovna T.N. Et al. the type, amount, and degree of infestation of weeds found in peas //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 5. – P. 678-682.

7. Turdiyeva N. et al. Study on the protective measures of agricultural crops fromweeds//E3SWeb of Conferences. - EDP Sciences, 2024. - T. 563. - P. 03015.

8. Turdiyeva N. et al. Efficiency of application of soil herbicides on chickpeas against annualdicotyledonous weeds . 3. - C. 37-39.

9. Turdiyeva N. et al. The type, amount, and degree of infestation of weeds foundinpeas//Galaxy international interdisciplinary research journal (GIIRJ), 2022. – T.

10. – P. 678-682. 10. Turdieva N. Sayfullaeva N and others. Influence of herbicidal norms on cereal yieldwhilesowing on corn fields. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. ISSN 1475-7192. IJPR 10404 May 2020. – P. 4249 - 4253.

11. Turdieva N. Effects Of Herbicide Application Rates On Corn Yield In Maize Fields. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol.5Issue 2, February - 2021, - P.249-251.